

Studies on Indian Medicinal Plants. Part X.* Isolation of Neutral Components from *Glycosmis Arborea* (Roxb.) DC.**

S. C. Pakrashi, S. K. Roy, and J. Bhattacharyya

A detailed isolation procedure of two isomeric triterpene alcohols of a new type, viz., (a) arborinol (= arborinol A), m.p. 274°, $[\alpha]_D + 34.2^\circ$ (CHCl₃) and (b) iso-arborinol (= arborinol B), m.p. 298-99°, $[\alpha]_D + 45^\circ$ (CHCl₃), along with myricyl alcohol, m.p. 89-90°, stigmasterol and β -sitosterol from the neutral fraction of the light petroleum extract of the leaves of *Glycosmis arborea* (Roxb.) DC. has been described.

In a preliminary communication¹, the isolation of the neutral components of the leaves of *Glycosmis arborea* (Roxb.) DC. (Fam. Rutaceae) was reported from this laboratory. The present communication describes the detailed isolation procedure and the properties of the triterpenes.

The alkaloid-depleted² light petroleum extract of the plant material was resolved by column chromatography. Besides a large amount of oil, wax, myricyl alcohol (0.003%) (C₃₁H₆₂O, m.p. 89-90°), stigmasterol and β -sitosterol (0.005% each), we encountered two hitherto unknown epimeric³ triterpene alcohols, viz., arborinol (= arborinol A), m.p. 274°, $[\alpha]_D + 34.2^\circ$ and iso-arborinol (= arborinol B), m.p. 298-99°, $[\alpha]_D + 45^\circ$, in 0.022 and 0.003% respective yields.

Like the alkaloidal contents⁴, considerable seasonal variation in the yield of the triterpenes was observed. For example, the triterpene content was found to increase with the maturity of the leaves, being the minimum in May—June and maximum in November—December. The variation in the yield of the fatty alcohol has been found to be just the reverse.

With Burchard-Liberman reagent, arborinol exhibited a deep blue colour immediately at the interface, changing to indigo-blue, whereas iso-arborinol very sluggishly developed a faint violet colour. Tetranitromethane produced a yellow colour with the former, but not with the latter. None of them absorbs in the UV region.

Arborinol is freely soluble, but iso-arborinol is less so in benzene, ether, and chloroform. Both of them are sparingly soluble in light petroleum, ethanol, and methanol.

*Part IX. Pakrashi and Ghosh-Dastidar, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1964, 2, 379.

**For a discussion of the correct species involved vide Ref. 2.

1. Pakrashi and Roy, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1961, 20B, 186.

2. Pakrashi et al., *Ann. Biochem. Exptl. Med.*, 1963, 23, 123; *Tetrahedron*, 1963, 19, 1011.

3. *Annalen*, 1963, 668, 57.

4. Chakravarti and Chakravarti, *J. Proc. Inst. Chem.*, 1952, 24, 96.

Arborinol afforded a monoacetate, m.p. 240°, $[\alpha]_D + 12.7^\circ$, in 75% yield and a monobenzoate, m.p. 232-33°, $[\alpha]_D + 40^\circ$. Under identical reaction conditions, iso-arborinol formed an acetate, m.p. 288-89°, $[\alpha]_D + 54^\circ$, in almost quantitative yield and a benzoate, m.p. 330°, $[\alpha]_D + 66.5^\circ$.

The provisional¹ formulations, $C_{29-30}H_{46-50}O$ and $C_{30}H_{52}O$, for arborinol and iso-arborinol respectively, have now been revised³ to $C_{30}H_{50}O$ for both on the basis of analyses of the original compounds and their derivatives and particularly the mass spectrum of the common ketone (m/e 424 for M^+ ion), arborinone, $C_{30}H_{48}O$, m.p. 216°, $[\alpha]_D + 28.8^\circ$. This ketone (IR in chloroform, 5.9μ for 6-membered ring $>C=O$), obtained by chromic acid oxidation of the triterpenes in pyridine, exhibited a negative Cotton effect in optical rotatory dispersion curve³, quite rare for a pentacyclic triterpene with a 3-keto group⁵. The fragmentation pattern in the mass spectrum was also unusual³ in that it did not resemble the fragmentation pattern of the usual α - or β -amyrin. The expected peak at m/e 205 for a 3-keto compound⁶ is conspicuously absent. Instead, there is a strong peak at m/e 257.

Arborinone or sodium borohydride reduction predominantly yielded iso-arborinol, thus establishing the epimeric nature and configuration of the hydroxyl function of the triterpene alcohols.

On the basis of extensive chemical and physical methods, Vorbrüggen, Pakrashi, and Djerassi³ have been able to establish the structure and stereochemistry of rings A, B, and C as well as the presence of two secondary and one tertiary methyl groups in both of them. These are thus 3-hydroxy- $\Delta^{9(11)}$ -13 β ,14 α -dimethyl pentacyclic triterpenes of a novel structural type (I). Uncertainty, however, remains as to the stereochemistry of the methyl groups at positions 17, 19, and 20.

Ia: Arborinol, OH = α .

Ib: Iso-arborinol, OH = β .

EXPERIMENTAL

Isolation of Neutral Compounds.—Air-dried and milled leaves (3 kg.) of *Glycosmis arborea* were Soxhletted with light petroleum for about 20 hr. The extract was concen-

*Melting points are uncorrected. Petroleum ether, b.p. 60-80°, and neutral alumina for chromatography (Riedel-de-Haen AG) were used. The optical rotations were measured in chloroform solution.

5. Djerassi *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, **81**, 4587.

6. Budzikiewicza *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1963, **85**, 3689.

trated to about 200 ml, cooled in a refrigerator overnight, and filtered to remove the precipitated alkaloids. The filtrate was then extracted with 2*N*-HCl till free of the basic components⁷. The organic layer was then washed, dried, concentrated, and filtered through a column of alumina (45 × 4 cm). The light petroleum (Fraction A) and light petroleum with increasing proportions of benzene as well as pure benzene eluates (Fraction B) were then chromatographed in separate columns (30 × 4 cm).

The subsequent benzene and chloroform extracts of the plant yielded only an oil and small amounts of stigmasterol from the respective neutral parts. Therefore in the later runs, the plant materials were extracted only with light petroleum and after the separation of arborinine⁷ the extract was directly chromatographed with the same result since the alkaloids did not interfere with the neutral components.

Isolation of Myricyl Alcohol and Arborinol.—The crude concentrate of Fraction A on chromatography, using light petroleum as eluent, separated a waxy material and then large amounts of an oil, followed by a straight-chain fatty alcohol (IR), m. p. 83-90°, crystallising from ethylacetate-benzene or better acetone in 0.003% yield. Its analytical data correspond to C₃₁H₆₄O, believed to be myricyl alcohol* from the physical constants. (Found: C, 82.34; H, 14.29. Calc. for C₃₁H₆₄O: C, 82.43; H, 14.05%).

Further elution with light petroleum-benzene (10-20%; 8 litres) and crystallisations of the product from benzene-acetone afforded fine white needles of *arborinol* in 0.022% yield. It was purified through its acetate and analysed; m.p. 274°, [α]_D +34.2° (c, 0.75). (Found: C, 84.37; H, 11.60. C₃₀H₅₀O requires C, 84.44; H, 11.81%).

The *monoacetate* was prepared by treatment with acetic anhydride and pyridine either at 3° for 12 hr. in 75% yield or by refluxing for 4 hr., followed by chromatography, using light petroleum as eluent. It crystallised from benzene-methanol in white needles, m.p. 240°, [α]_D +12.7° (c, 1.1). (Found: C, 82.24; H, 11.32. C₃₂H₅₈O₂ requires C, 82.00; H, 11.19%). The acetate on hydrolysis with even 20% EtOH-KOH for 4 hr. regenerated the original compound.

The *monobenzoate*, prepared by refluxing with benzoyl chloride and pyridine, was crystallised from benzene-methanol in white needles, m.p. 232-33°, [α]_D +40° (c, 1.0). (Found: C, 83.64; H, 10.12. C₃₇H₅₄O₂ requires C, 83.72; H, 10.25%).

Isolation of Stigmasterol, β-Sitosterol, and Iso-arborinol.—Fraction B on elution with light petroleum-benzene (30-50%) yielded sterols, proved to be a mixture of stigmasterol (0.005%), m.p. 169-70°, [α]_D -51.7°, benzoate m.p. 160-61°, [α]_D -29° and β-sitosterol (0.005%), m.p. 137°, [α]_D -35°, benzoate m.p. 145°, [α]_D -16°, when purified through their derivatives indicated⁸, and also from correct analyses.

Light petroleum-benzene (60%) eluted another triterpene, which on crystallisation from benzene afforded white fine needles of *iso-arborinol*, m.p. 298-99°, [α]_D +45° (c, 0.8), in 0.003% yield. (Found: C, 84.05; H, 11.30. C₃₀H₅₀O requires C, 84.44; H, 11.81%).

*Authentic specimen was not available for direct comparison.

7. Pakrashi *et al.*, *Chem. & Ind.*, 1961, 464.

8. Roy and Pakrashi, *Ann. Biochem. Exptl. Med.*, 1960, 20, 144.

The *monooacetate*, m.p. 288-89°, $[\alpha]_D + 54^\circ$ (c. 1.26), was obtained almost in quantitative yield when iso-arborinol was treated with acetic anhydride in pyridine at 3° for 12 hr. (Found: C, 82.12; H, 11.28. $C_{32}H_{52}O_2$ requires C, 82.00; H, 11.19%). Benzoate, m.p. 330°, $[\alpha]_D + 66.5^\circ$ (c. 0.54). (Found: C, 83.83; H, 9.93. $C_{37}H_{54}O_2$ requires C, 83.72; H, 10.25%).

Chromic Acid Oxidation of Arborinol and Iso-arborinol: Preparation of Arborinone.—Chromic acid (0.25 g.) was gradually added to an ice-cold solution of arborinol (0.2 g.) in pyridine (25 ml) with constant stirring and the mixture was left at the room temperature for about 20 hr. The crude product (0.13 g.), obtained by the usual work-up, was chromatographed over a column (10 × 1 cm) of alumina. The material, eluted with light petroleum (120 ml), on crystallisation from benzene-methanol furnished white needles (0.1 g.) of *arborinone*, m.p. 216°, $[\alpha]_D + 28.8^\circ$ (c. 0.76). The same ketone (mixed m.p., IR) was obtained when iso-arborinol was similarly treated. (Found: C, 84.84; H, 11.30. $C_{30}H_{48}O$ requires C, 84.84; H, 11.39%).

Sodium Borohydride Reduction of Arborinone.—The method followed was essentially the same as adopted by Djerassi *et al*⁹. Sodium borohydride (0.15 g.) was added to a cold solution of arborinone (0.05 g.) in methanol and left at the room temperature overnight, when a white solid separated. The mixture was refluxed on a water bath for about 1½ hr. and poured on ice containing HCl (1 ml, conc.). After being heated on the steam bath for 30 min., the product was extracted with ether. The white residue, obtained after usual work-up, on chromatography, followed by crystallisation from benzene-methanol, afforded iso-arborinol, m.p. 298-99°.

Support (grant N.H-4320) for this investigation by the National Heart Institute, U.S. Public Health Service, is gratefully acknowledged. The authors are indebted to the authorities of M/s. Bengal Chemical and Pharmaceutical Works, Calcutta, for the large-scale extraction of the plant materials. Microanalyses were done by Dr. A. Bernhardt, Mülheim, W. Germany, as well as Dr. G. Weiler and F. Strauss of Oxford, U.K.

INDIAN INSTITUTE FOR BIOCHEMISTRY AND
EXPERIMENTAL MEDICINE,
CALCUTTA-32.

Received June 17, 1964.